

Pathways to Universal Energy Access in Northern Brazil: Modeling with OnSSET

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OnSSET, Brazil, Amazônia, LCOE, 2050, Universalization.

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Executive Summary

This study analyzed strategies for universal access to electricity in the state of Amapá by 2050, showing that the electrification of approximately 887,000 inhabitants can be achieved with an investment of around US\$250 million and a total capacity of approximately 73 MW in a Business As Usual scenario. The results show that the expansion and densification of the electricity grid play a central role, especially in denser areas, while isolated and hybrid photovoltaic solar systems stand out as technically and economically viable solutions for remote regions. Even when penalized in terms of cost, solar energy maintains a high share, confirming its robustness and strong adherence to the regional solar potential. The scenario favoring wind energy introduces greater technological diversification, with the insertion of wind generation in coastal areas with greater potential. However, this alternative implies greater implementation complexity and a possible increase in costs, without replacing the relevance of solar energy. Based on these results, it is recommended to prioritize the expansion of the grid in urban areas, expand the use of off-grid solar systems in isolated communities, and develop wind projects directed towards the coast. Additionally, the need to incorporate long-term climate data is highlighted, reducing uncertainties associated with the use of limited time series and increasing the reliability of energy planning.

Figura 1 - Mapa brasileiro em comparação com a América do Sul. O SIN conecta todos estados brasileiros a um único sistema de energia, entretanto muitas regiões não são atendidas por ele, e sim pelos SISOL.

1. Introduction

Brazil occupies about half of the territory of South America, with more than 8.5 million km², and has a population exceeding 213 million inhabitants (IBGE, 2022, 2024). This vast territory presents a great diversity of energy resources, both renewable and non-renewable. In the context of the electricity sector, all Brazilian states are connected to the National Interconnected System (SIN), an extensive network that integrates energy generation, transmission, and distribution. However, this network does not cover the entire territory (ONS, 2023).

In remote regions, especially in the Amazon, connection to the National Interconnected System (SIN) is limited by technical and economic issues. As observed in Figura 1, while the South, Southeast, Midwest, and Northeast regions have consolidated electrical infrastructure, the North region presents significant gaps, characterized by the presence of Isolated Systems (SISOL), which generally use fossil fuel generation. These areas represent important challenges for the universalization of access to energy, with approximately 1

million people still without electricity service (IEMA, 2020).

Given this context, the Amazon is considered the country's main energy frontier. In this context, the study proposes to analyze scenarios for universal access to electricity by 2050 in the state of Amapá using geospatial modeling with the OnSSET tool, aiming to support regional energy planning.

2. Methodology

The study area presented in this report is Amapá, one of the 26 states of Brazil, given its weaknesses in connection to the National Interconnected System (SIN) and its lack of efficient planning to achieve universal electricity access (see Figure 2).

The creation of scenarios in OnSSET is essentially fed by geospatial data from the study area and can be summarized in the following flowchart in Figure 3. However, before starting the first stage (Geodatabase Building), it was necessary to adapt the data for the following stages. Each of the datasets (also called layers) in Table 1 went through two stages: the first was done to ensure that the information contained in the file refers to the state of Amapá; the second was to confirm and, if necessary, change the CRS (Coordinate Reference System) of the layer to the global CRS: EPSG 4326.

Figure 2- Highlighting the study area of this report, the state of Amapá, located in the far north of Brazil, where it borders the countries of French Guiana and Suriname and, in the south, the state of Pará.

These two steps were performed using QGIS 3.10.7 software, employing the *clip* and *reproject* functions (*warp* in the case of raster layers).

Figure 3- Flowchart of the steps taken to develop scenarios for universalizing access to electricity in Amapá using OnSSET.

The table below shows each dataset used, its type (vector or raster), and its origin.

Table 1- Geodataset used for developing scenarios for Amapá in 2050.

Dataset	Type	Source
Administrative Boundaries (ADMIN1 and ADMIN2)	Vector (Polygon)	Global Administrative Areas Database (GADM)
Global Horizontal Irradiance	Raster	Global Solar Atlas
Wind Speed	Raster	Global Wind Atlas
Night-Time Lights (NTL)	Raster	EOG Data Mines

Travel Time (TT)	Raster	Weiss et al. (2018)
Existing High Voltage Lines (Existing HV)	Vector (Lines)	Brazilian Energy Research Company (EPE) WebMap
Planned High Voltage Lines (Planned HV)	Vector (Lines)	Brazilian Energy Research Company (EPE) WebMap
Existing Medium Voltage Lines (Existing MV)	Vector (Lines)	ANEEL Open Data (BDGD)
Hydropoints	Vector (Points)	Brazilian Energy Research Company (EPE) WebMap
Population	Raster	WorldPop Hub – Population Counts
Roads	Vector (Lines)	World Bank Group - Road Network
Substations	Vector (Points)	Brazilian Energy Research Company (EPE) WebMap
Distributions Transformers	Vector (Points)	ANEEL Open Data (BDGD)

The CSV Preparation stage was performed in Jupyter Notebook, using Anaconda, a complete Python distribution geared towards data science. This platform allows the creation of separate computing environments with different libraries. In this phase, the datasets were integrated into a single CSV file and redesigned to the CRS 5880 coordinate reference system, appropriate for the region and with units in meters.

In the next step, CSV Calibration, the data were adjusted considering the initial year of the modeling, defined as 2022, based on the latest Brazilian demographic census. The final step consisted of creating scenarios for 2050, divided into two cases. The parameters used in the two scenarios can be seen in Table 2.

- 1) Business As Usual: uses parameters obtained from reliable sources, with hourly irradiance, temperature, and wind data from 2019 collected in the center of Amapá;
- 2) Favorability for Wind Energy: alters costs, increasing solar energy by 30% and reducing wind energy by 50%, in addition to using climate data from the coast, where wind potential is greater and assuming its greater share in the coming years.

Table 2- Parameters used for modeling scenarios for universal access to electricity in Amapá by the year 2050.

Variable	Value	
	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Start year	2022	2022
End year	2050	2050
Electrification rate target in 2050	1	1
Electrification rate modeled in 2022	0.7476579	0.7476579
Urban target tier	5	5
Rural target tier large	4	4
Rural target tier small	3	3
Intensification distance	50	50
Maximum intensification cost (USD/household)	6000	6000

Population in 2022	733758	733758
Population in 2050	887384	887384
Urban ratio 2022	0.89995703	0.89995703
Urban ratio 2050	0.95	0.95
Grid generation cost (USD/kWh)	0.1	0.1
Grid power plants capital cost (USD/kW)	600	600
Grid losses	0.15	0.15
Diesel price (USD/L)	2	2
MG Hydro capital cost (USD/kW)	{inf: 1200}	{inf: 2000}
Minimum MG size	50	20
MG Minimum grid distance	1	1
MG Interconnection	1	1
PV cost (USD/kW)	1000	1300
Battery cost (USD/kWh)	250	250
Inverter cost (USD/kW)	300	300
Diesel generation cost (USD/kW)	300	300
Maximum diesel	0	0
SA PV capital cost 1 (USD/kW)	10000	13000
SA PV capital cost 2 (USD/kW)	7000	9100
SA PV capital cost 3 (USD/kW)	5000	7200
SA PV capital cost 4 (USD/kW)	4000	5200
SA PV capital cost 5 (USD/kW)	2500	3500
Grid MV line cost	100000	100000
Grid LV line cost	20000	20000
Grid MV line capacity	34.5	34.5
Grid LV line capacity	0.24	0.24
Grid LV line max length	1.5	1.5
HV line cost	1,000,000	1,000,000
Maximum grid extension distance	80	80
Annual new grid connections limit	6000	6000
Grid capacity limit	10000	10000
Grid discount rate	0.06	0.06
Minimum grid discount rate	0.08	0.08
SA discount rate	0.15	0.15

Each scenario considers five technology options to meet the electrical demands of the population groups (settlements):

- Grid Density and Grid Extension: existing electrical grid and its expansion to meet new demands;
- SA PV: Stand-Alone Photovoltaic systems, solar power systems without connection to the electrical grid, off-grid;
- MG PV-Hybrid: Mini-grid supplied by the conventional electricity distribution network and by photovoltaic systems;
- MG Wind: Mini-Grid powered exclusively by wind turbines;
- MG Hydro: Mini-Grid supplied exclusively by hydroelectric power generation plants.

3. Results

3.1 First Scenario – Business As Usual:

According to the scenario developed by OnSSET, the population served by each technology in 2050 will be:

Figure 4- Population served by each technology up to the year 2050.

By the year 2050, each technology will receive a total number of new connections, which can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5- New connections of settlements to different technologies by the year 2050.

Of the technologies used until 2050 to universalize access to electricity, each technology will have an installed capacity in MW as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6- Installed capacity of each technology up to the year 2050.

To achieve this result by the end of 2050, each technology will cost a value in millions of US dollars, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7- Total investment by technology until the year 2050.

Finally, for this scenario, it is possible to observe the map below (Figure 8) showing the technologies used and where they are concentrated.

Figure 8- Map showing the distribution of technologies used to achieve universal access to electricity by the year 2050 in the state of Amapá, Brazil.

3.2 Second Scenario – Favorability for Wind Energy:

The same data was generated for the second scenario, but with differences in the technologies used.

Figure 9- Population served by each technology up to the year 2050.

Figure 10- New connections of settlements to different technologies by the year 2050.

Figure 11- Installed capacity of each technology up to the year 2050.

Figure 12- Total investment by technology until the year 2050.

Figure 13- Tons of CO2 generated directly during the electricity generation process by each type of technology up to the year 2050.

Figure 14- Map showing the distribution of technologies used to universalize electricity access by 2050 in the state of Amapá, Brazil. Highlighting the role of wind turbines off the coast of the state.

5. Discussion:

The results obtained from the graphs indicate that expanding access to electricity in the state of Amapá by 2050 will depend on a combination of technologies, with emphasis on extending the existing grid, photovoltaic solar systems and, to a lesser extent, hybrid and MG solutions.

In the Business As Usual scenario, it is observed that the majority of the population served is associated with grid intensification (Grid Density), followed by isolated solar PV systems (SA PV) and hybrid photovoltaic systems. This behavior reflects the continuity of current trends in electricity grid expansion coupled with the increasing use of decentralized solutions – a scenario currently on the rise in the state. The share of solar energy is particularly relevant in both scenarios, and this can be seen in the comparisons of the graphs in Figure 15 and Figure 16.

Figure 15- Comparison between the installed capacity in MW of each technology used in the scenario. Note the large installed capacity of SA PV even in an unfavorable scenario.

Figure 16- Comparison of investments up to the year 2050 in the technologies addressed in the scenarios. Even with virtually high prices, PV systems receive the largest share of investments in both scenarios. However, in the first scenario the total invested is US\$ 250.08 million and in the second US\$ 341.29 million.

In the first scenario, solar PV systems have high installed capacity and absorb a significant portion of total investments, indicating their economic and technical attractiveness for remote regions. This result is consistent with the high solar potential of the Northern region of Brazil, evidenced by the availability of global irradiance data used in the model and with national data (SENAI et al., 2024; Pereira et al., 2017).

In the second scenario, even though the costs of solar technology have increased, its share remains significant. This result reinforces the idea that Amapá's high solar potential, combined with the technological maturity of photovoltaic systems, makes this source essential for universal access to energy. On the other hand, the scenario favoring wind energy introduces important changes in the technological matrix.

Cost reductions and the use of coastal climate data have resulted in the integration of wind power (MG Wind), especially in coastal regions. Although wind energy's share is still smaller compared to solar and the electrical grid, there is a significant increase in its contribution to installed capacity and diversification of the energy matrix. This behavior aligns with the greater wind potential of coastal areas in Amapá, where higher wind speeds favor generation. Thus, the second scenario highlights the strategic role of wind energy as a complement to other sources, especially in locations with suitable natural conditions.

Before comparing the scenarios, it is important to highlight that, due to OnSSET's operating methodology and the division of population clusters into small settlements, even in large urban areas, parts of the model may not reflect reality – for example: a single cluster in the middle of an urban center surrounded by other clusters served by the distribution network (Grid Extension or Grid Density) that is served by a PV system. This indicates that OnSSET analyzed the cluster separately and, due to the low electricity demand, concluded that the lowest-cost option for that location would be a solar system.

Aside from this limitation in the model, the comparison of the two scenarios reveals some important differences. The Business As Usual scenario tends to be cheaper in terms of total investment (S1 = US\$ 250.08 million; S2 = US\$ 341.29 million), since it maintains lower costs for solar energy and does not depend on the additional deployment of wind infrastructure. Furthermore, the strong dependence on the electricity grid can represent greater reliability in urban and more densely populated areas. However, this same dependence can limit flexibility and increase vulnerability in remote regions.

On the other hand, the scenario favoring wind energy presents greater technological diversification, which can contribute to greater resilience of the energy system and reduces dependence on a single renewable source, potentially improving reliability in specific locations, especially coastal areas. However, this scenario tends to demand higher investments and greater implementation complexity due to the need for additional infrastructure and the integration of different technologies.

In summary, the Business As Usual scenario stands out for its lower cost and operational simplicity, while the scenario with greater wind power participation offers advantages in terms of diversification and utilization of regional natural resources. The choice between the two will depend on the desired balance between cost, energy security, and sustainable use of available resources.

7. Conclusion

The results indicate that universal access to electricity in Amapá by 2050 is feasible, requiring investments of around US\$250 million in the Business As Usual scenario, with a total installed capacity of approximately 72.9 MW and serving about 887,000 people. In this scenario, the strong dependence on the grid (Grid Density) — responsible for serving more than 680,000 people — demonstrates the relevance of the existing infrastructure for expanding access. Solar

energy plays a strategic role, with approximately 25 MW installed in isolated systems (SA PV) and the largest individual investments (\approx US\$138.9 million).

In scenarios favorable to wind energy, greater technological diversification and the integration of wind turbines are observed, especially in coastal areas, increasing the system's resilience. However, this diversification comes with increased operational complexity and a potential rise in total costs, due to the need for integration between different sources.

Comparatively, the Business As Usual scenario proves to be more economical and simpler to implement, while the scenario with wind power tends to be more resilient and adapted to regional characteristics. A limitation is the dependence on point climate data (year 2019 and specific locations), which may not fully capture the interannual variability of solar and wind resources. Furthermore, improvements in the population cluster layer could lead to more reliable results that reflect reality.

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